

STUDIES IN INDIGOID DYES. PART VI

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The 7-chloro derivatives of *bis*-2-thionaphthene-ethylene indigo, 2-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene-indigo and its 2'-nitro derivative, benzylidene-2-thionaphthene and two of its substituted compounds have been prepared. The dyeing shades of the thioindigoid dyes have been studied on wool and on cotton and those of the thioindogenides on wool only.

In previous parts of this series of papers one of us (Guha, this *Journal*, 1935, 12, 659; 1937, 14, 709; 1938, 15, 359; 1944, 21, 391; 1946, 23, 103) studied the influence of a methyl radical when present in every different available position of the thionaphthene nucleus of *bis*-2-thionaphthene-ethylene-indigo, 2-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene-indigo and its 2'-nitro derivative, benzylidene-2-thionaphthene and its *p*-nitro-, and *p*-dimethylamino derivatives (Friedländer and Risse, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 1919; Friedländer, Herzog and Voss, *ibid.*, 1922, 55, 1591; Pummerer and Luther, *Ber.*, 1931, 64, 831; Dutt, this *Journal*, 1932, 9, 99; Friedländer, *Monatsh.*, 1909, 30, 347).

In this communication, a few compounds having a chlorine atom in the 7-position of the thionaphthene ring of the dye molecules stated above have been studied primarily with the object of observing if the change in colour of the isomeric (4-, 5-, 6-, 7- chloro) thionaphthene indigos, also takes place in the same way as already found in the case of isomeric (4-, 5-, 6-, 7- methyl)-thionaphthene-indigos (Guha, *loc. cit.*). Secondly, because instances belonging to symmetrical and asymmetrical thioindigoid dyes and also thioindogenides having any type of substituent solely in the 7-position of the thionaphthene ring of the dye molecule are few only (cf. Guha, this *Journal*, 1943, 20, 37; 1944, 21, 87; Dalgleish and Mann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 893; Guha and Chatterjea, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 473; 1948, 25, 429).

7-Chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (Dalgleish and Mann, *loc. cit.*) was therefore condensed with glyoxal, phenanthraquinone and its 2-nitro derivative, benzaldehyde, *p*-nitro- and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde respectively and the corresponding new products obtained.

The thioindigoid dyes as well as the thioindogenides described here are all crystalline substances. The products of former class are all soluble in nitrobenzene and the compounds of latter class dissolve easily in pyridine, xylene and nitrobenzene. The products of both the classes dissolve in cold strong sulphuric acid producing a characteristic colour from which water precipitates the original substances suitable for dyeing on wool from an acid bath. The dyeing shades of the first four compounds on wool and those of the second and third dyes on cotton from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat were not fully developed. It was found easier to work with the 2-(7-chloro)thionaphthene-9'-(2'-nitro) phenanthrene-indigo in developing shades on cotton from the alkaline vat than the mother compound which was not reduced easily, similar to what was experienced in the case of isomeric (methyl) thionaphthene-phenanthrene-indigos (Guha, *loc. cit.*).

Further studies in the 5-chloro series of the class of compounds have been undertaken.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

bis-2-(7-Chloro)-thionaphthene-ethylene-indigo

A solution of glyoxal sodium bisulphite (1.136 g.) in water (30 c.c.) was mixed with 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (1.476 g.) dissolved previously in absolute alcohol (50 c.c.). The mixture was treated with strong hydrochloric acid (8c.c.) and heated for 1½ hours on the water-bath. The separated crystalline dye (0.47g.) was collected, washed with hot water and crystallised from nitrobenzene in long violet-red needles melting above 320°. It is moderately soluble in pyridine, xylene, benzene, acetic acid, alcohol and carbon tetrachloride. Strong sulphuric acid dissolves it producing a leafy green solution from which water precipitates the original dye. It dyes wool in violet-red shade from an acid bath and cotton in deep violet-red shade from a deep yellow alkaline hydrosulphite vat. (Found : Cl, 18.38. $C_{18}H_8O_2Cl_2S_2$ requires Cl, 18.16 per cent).

2-(7-Chloro)-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene-indigo

Phenanthraquinone (0.63 g.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.55 g.) were dissolved in boiling glacial acetic acid (40 c.c.). The resulting solution when gradually treated with strong hydrochloric acid (4 c.c.), separated a thick brownish red crystalline mass. After heating for 10 minutes, the dye (0.67 g.) was collected, washed with a little glacial acetic acid, water and finally crystallised from xylene in needles melting at 306° with previous shrinking at 304°. The product is soluble in pyridine, xylene, benzene; moderately soluble in acetic acid, carbon tetrachloride; sparingly soluble in alcohol. The solution of the substance in cold strong sulphuric acid is light green. It dyes wool in light *khaki* brown shade from an acid bath and cotton in light violet shade from a light yellow alkaline hydrosulphite vat obtained at 75°-80°. (Found : Cl, 9.2. $C_{22}H_{11}O_2ClS$ requires Cl, 9.47 per cent).

2-(7-Chloro)-thionaphthene-9'-(2'-nitro)-phenanthrene-indigo separated at once in deep brownish red crystals when a solution of 2-nitrophenanthraquinone (0.69 g.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.55 g.) in boiling glacial acetic acid (42 c.c.) were treated with strong hydrochloric acid (2 c.c.). The mixture was heated for 10 minutes and cooled to room temperature (30°). The dye (0.90 g.) was collected, washed with acetic acid, water and crystallised thrice from nitrobenzene in bundles of pointed needles decomposing and subliming above 326°. It is soluble in pyridine and tetralin; moderately soluble in xylene, benzene and carbon tetrachloride; sparingly soluble in alcohol. It dissolves in cold strong sulphuric acid producing a deep green solution. It dyes wool in violet-brown shade from an acid bath and cotton in violet colour from an yellow alkaline hydrosulphite vat at 60°-70°. (Found: N, 3.34. $C_{22}H_{10}O_4NCIS$ requires N, 3.33 per cent).

Benzylidene-2-(7-chloro)-thionaphthene

It separated in yellow needles from a solution of benzaldehyde (0.42 g.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.738 g.) in absolute alcohol (16 c.c.) when treated with strong hydrochloric acid (2 c.c.) and heated for 20 minutes only. The product (0.718 g.) was crystallised from alcohol in long yellow needles melting at 161-62°. It is soluble in benzene, carbon tetrachloride and acetic acid. The solution of the substance in cold strong sulphuric acid is of violet-red colour. It dyes wool in yellow shade from an acid bath. (Found: S, 11.66. $C_{15}H_9OClS$ requires S, 11.72 per cent).

4'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(7-chloro)-thionaphthene was obtained in a similar way from *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.604 g.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.738 g.) which were dissolved in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.), treated with strong hydrochloric acid (4 c.c.) and heated for a few minutes only. The separated crystalline product (0.828 g.) was crystallised from benzene in pleasant, shining yellow, long pointed needles, m.p. 280-281°. The substance is moderately soluble in benzene, acetic acid; sparingly soluble in alcohol and carbon tetrachloride. Strong sulphuric acid dissolves it producing a bluish violet solution in cold. It dyes wool in a pleasant bright yellow uniform shade from an acid bath. (Found: N, 4.66. $C_{15}H_8O_3NCIS$ requires N, 4.4 per cent).

4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(7-chloro)-thionaphthene.—Its hydrochloride separated as yellow rectangular plates from *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.596 g.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.738 g.) when dissolved in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.), treated with strong hydrochloric acid (25 c.c.), heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour on the water-bath and cooled to 40°. The product (0.981 g.) on washing with dilute alcohol (1:1) turned yellowish red; it was washed well with dilute ammonium hydroxide and hot water. It was crystallised from alcohol in rectangular shining plates, m.p. 187-88°. It is soluble in acetic acid, benzene, carbon tetrachloride; moderately soluble in alcohol. It dissolves in cold strong sulphuric acid giving beautiful violet solution which on dilution with water first turns light yellow and then the original substance is precipitated. It dyes wool in pleasant red-orange uniform shade from an acid bath. (Found: N, 4.71. $C_{17}H_{14}ONClS$ requires N, 4.4 per cent).